

Original Article

Comparative Analysis of Slot Deformation Between Orthodontic Brackets with Varied Tie Wings

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Orthodontics deals with the treatment of malocclusion of teeth using orthodontic brackets, archwires, and ligatures etc. as components of fixed appliances. Orthodontic brackets are available with different geometry, material and tip / torque prescription. Bracket slot may be prone for deformation due to the archwire torquing forces. The aim of this study was to analyse the slot deformation between Four Tie Wings (4-TW) and Six Tie Wings (6-TW) brackets using Finite Element Analysis (FEA). Stainless Steel (SS) 0.0223 preadjusted 4-TW and 6-TW brackets along with SS 0.0213 × 0.0253 archwires were modelled by reverse engineering approach. In the Finite Element (FE) model, the archwires were twisted from 5° to 40°. The deformation in the Top Location of Slot (TLS) and Middle Location of Slot (MLS) of 4-TW and 6-TW brackets were measured. Results showed that the slot deformation of the 6-TW bracket was 2.57 times lesser than 4-TW bracket. The maximum deformation was seen in the TLS compared to MLS in both the brackets. Our FEA study showed that the 6-TW brackets are better than 4-TW brackets in relevance to slot deformation and thus advantageous in reducing the torque loss.

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Introduction

Malocclusion is improper alignment of teeth that affects the facial aesthetics and function. Irrespective of the age, the number of patients seeking malocclusion treatment is growing rapidly. Malocclusion is treated using orthodontic fixed appliances consisting of orthodontic brackets, archwires, ligatures, coil springs etc. Due to the advancement in materials and manufacturing technology, different material composition are used for brackets as well as with varying geometry such as conventional, self-ligating and pre-adjusted. Bracket-archwire assembly works with the principles of mechanics. Traditionally Four tie wings bracket are widely used in orthodontics. Rectangular archwires generated torque applied on the tooth through brackets facilitates finer tooth movement. Due to the applied labial crown or lingual root torque, brackets are subjected to stress, strain and deformation.

Experimental and FE Studies extensively evaluated the torque of commonly used archwires [1-3]. Few studies quantified the stress in the brackets and archwires [4,5]. Experimental studies using digital image correlation technique showed that the tie wings in the 4-TW brackets deformed due to the application of archwire torque [6,7]. An experimental study showed that bracket tie wings are strained by the force application [8]. FE and experimental studies showed that the 4-TW bracket slot deformation may contribute to torque loss [9-11]. Interestingly, tie wings rotation in 4-TW bracket was revealed in a FE study [12]. A FE study showed that the slot deformation of 4-TW bracket was higher compared to tie wings deformation as slots have a direct contact with twisted archwire [13].

Six TW brackets was introduced due to its less friction, alignment efficiency and better tooth control in mesio-distal direction. A FE study analysed archwire tipping induced stress and deformation in 6-TW brackets [14]. If brackets deformed due to the applied torque, then the expected torque may not be transferred to the tooth which affects the final tooth position. Clinically, a bracket which can withstand the archwire torque with less slot deformation

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would be beneficial for effective torque transfer. To the best of our knowledge, no studies are available comparing the slot deformation between 4-TW and 6-TW brackets for the applied torque. FEA is an excellent and widely used method that helps to test the mechanical behaviour of structures without extensive experimentation and instruments. So, the aim of this study was to analyze the archwire torque induced slot deformation between 4-TW and 6-TW brackets using FEA.

Materials and Methods

A maxillary central incisor SS 0.0223 preadjusted 4-TW bracket (G & H Orthodontics, Franklin, USA) and maxillary central incisor SS 0.0223 preadjusted 6-TW bracket (Synergy® SWLF System, Rocky Mountain Orthodontics, Denver, USA) were used in this study. The bracket's dimensions were measured through the Profile projector (ph 3515F; Mitutoyo' Takatsu-Ku, Japan) under 10x magnification as shown in Figure 1a. The solid model of both brackets were developed using modelling software (SOLIDWORKS Corp. Dassault Systems, Vélizy-Villacoublay, France) as shown in Figures 1b and 1c. The 0.0213 × 0.0253 archwire was modelled and assembled in a bracket slot using SOLIDWORKS as shown in Figures 1b and 1c. The 4-TW and 6-TW brackets were imported to Ansys Workbench (Ansys, Inc. USA) for the development of the FE model.

Brackets and archwires were meshed using a 0.05 mm hexahedral element for better accuracy. 4-TW and 6-TW bracket-archwire

assembly were consisted of 153833 elements, 135822 nodes and 185379 elements and 154867 nodes respectively as shown in Figures 1d and 1e. The mesh convergence was not performed as the bracket dimensions are less than 0.5 mm in curvature areas. So, a fine mesh was performed considering available computational facilities. The mesh quality was verified using jacobian, aspect ratio and skewness to ensure the precision of the FE model. The no separation contact connection was used between the gingival side of the slot wall and corresponding archwire face. The friction-less contact connection was used between the occlusal side of the slot wall and corresponding archwire face. Bracket slot base and corresponding archwire face were connected with bonded contact. All degrees of freedom in the nodes in the bracket base were fixed to simulate the bracket bonded on the tooth enamel surface in a clinical condition. The SS bracket and archwire were assigned with Young's modulus of 2×10^5 MPa and Poisson's ratio as 0.3 [15].

Palatal root torque of 0° to 40° with an interval of every 5° were applied using remote displacement. On the proximal view of the brackets, the Top Location of Slot (TLS) is the top corner of the slot wall in gingival and occlusal tie wings and the Middle Location of Slot (MLS) is exactly the middle point in the slot wall between the top corner and the base of the bracket as used in the literature [10].

Results and Discussion

The deformation of TLS and MLS of 4-TW and 6-TW 0.0223

Figure 1: Modelling and analysis of 4-TW and 6-TW bracket-archwire assembly: a. Profile projector used to measure the bracket dimensions, b. Solid model of 4-TW bracket with archwire c. Solid model of 6-TW bracket with archwire, d. FE model of 4-TW bracket-archwire assembly, e. FE model of 6-TW bracket-archwire assembly f. Deformed 4-TW bracket with twisted archwire and g. Deformed 6-TW bracket with twisted archwire

Figure 2: Graphical representation of comparative slot deformation between 4TW and 6TW brackets showing lesser deformation in 6-TW brackets than 4-TW brackets

brackets in 0.0213×0.0253 archwire were analyzed. For 40° angle of twist the deformation in the TLS was $10.56 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.10 \mu\text{m}$ in the 4-TW and 6-TW brackets respectively. Similarly, in the MLS it was $7.30 \mu\text{m}$ and $2.67 \mu\text{m}$ as presented in table 1.

There was no deformation in both brackets upto 5° of archwire twist due to the archwire play in the specific bracket-archwire combination. The maximum deformation was seen in the TLS compared to MLS in both 4-TW and 6-TW brackets as shown in Figures 1f and 1g. As the middle location of slot is closer to the base of the bracket, the deformation was lesser. Due to the cantilever nature of tie wings, the deformation in TLS was higher in both brackets. In the 4-TW bracket, for 40° angle of twist, the deformation in the TLS was $10.56 \mu\text{m}$. An experimental study reported that in the SS-4-TW self-ligating bracket, for 63° angle of twist, the deformation in the TLS was $7 \mu\text{m}$ to $70 \mu\text{m}$ [16]. In our study, the 4-TW bracket slot height was 0.0383 , so the deformation in the TLS was lesser than reported.

In this study, we have analysed the torque induced slot deformation in 6-TW brackets which was not reported in the literature. A FE study analysed the tipping force induced deformation and stress in

a 6-TW bracket without archwire model [14]. But, in our study, the slot deformation of the 6-TW bracket was measured with the archwire torquing force. A FE study showed that studying the slot deformation is more appropriate than tie wing deformation in the bracket-archwire interaction [13]. Thus, we compared the slot deformation of 4-TW and 6-TW brackets to visualize to the clinicians the deformation status of these brackets under torquing forces. The reduced deformation in the 6-TW compared to 4-TW are illustrated graphically in Figure 2. The torquing forces are dissipated to the more number of tie wings in the 6-TW brackets thus reducing the force exerted on the slot wall. In our study, deformation in the TLS and MLS of the 6-TW bracket were 2.57 times and 2.73 times lesser than the 4-TW bracket. It shows that the 6-TW brackets are advantageous compared to 4-TW brackets for reducing the torque loss because of lesser slot deformation.

The limitation of this study is that the tooth and its soft tissues were not included. Further, the dynamic behavior of slot deformation may vary between the brackets evaluated due to difference in the overall bracket and the tie wing dimensions, material composition, archwire size, composition and ligation methods.

Conclusion

This *in-silico* study compared the archwire torque induced slot deformation in 4-TW and 6-TW brackets. The 6-TW brackets showed lesser slot deformation than the 4-TW brackets. The deformation in the TLS was more than MLS in both the brackets. Thus, clinically the 6-TW brackets are advantageous compared to 4-TW brackets due to its lesser slot deformation and thus reduction in the torque loss in addition to lesser friction, increased alignment efficiency and better mesio-distal tooth control.

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References

1. Andrea W, Guggenbühl S, Hötzel L, et al., Comparing torque transmission of different bracket systems in combination with various archwires considering play in the bracket slot: an in vitro study, Materials. 17(3): 684, 1-16 (2024).

Table 1: Deformation in the TLS and MLS in 4-TW and 6-TW brackets for the various angles of archwire twist

Bracket model	4-TW bracket		6-TW bracket	
	Deformation (µm)			
Angle of twist (degree)	TLS	MLS	TLS	MLS
5	0	0	0	0
10	2.58	1.78	1.03	0.67
15	3.87	2.67	1.54	1.00
20	5.19	3.59	2.05	1.33
25	6.52	4.51	2.57	1.67
30	7.86	5.44	3.08	2.00
35	9.21	6.37	3.59	2.34
40	10.56	7.30	4.10	2.67

(4-TW: 4- Tie Wings, 6-TW: 6- Tie Wings, TLS: Top location of slot, MLS: Middle location of slot)

2. Papageorgiou SN, Sifakakis I, Keilig L, et al., Torque differences according to tooth morphology and bracket placement: a finite element study, *Eur. J. Orthod.* 39(4), 411–418 (2017).
3. Bernisha RP, Mishra G, Pradeep Raj G, et al., Incisor torque expression characteristics in two passive self-ligating brackets placed at different heights. A finite element investigation, *J. Oral Biol. Craniofac. Res.* 14(1), 98-106 (2024).
4. Benaissa A, Merdji A, Bendjaballah MZ, et al., Stress influence on orthodontic system components under simulated treatment loadings, *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 195, 105569 (2020).
5. Chun Y, Lee Y, Lee H, et al., Analytical study for prediction of stress distribution on orthodontic archwire considering short-term stress loss, *Comput. Methods Biomech. Biomed. Engin.* 26(14)1752–1760 (2022).
6. Lacoursiere RA, Nobes DS, Homeniuk DL, et al., Measurement of orthodontic bracket tie wing elastic and plastic deformation by arch wire torque expression utilizing an optical image correlation technique, *J Dent Biomech.* 1-8 397037 (2010).
7. Melenka GW, Nobes DS, Major PW, et al., Three-dimensional deformation of orthodontic brackets, *J Dent Biomech.* 4 (2013).
8. Matsui S, Umezaki E, Komazawa D, et al., Evaluation of mechanical properties of esthetic brackets, *J Dent Biomech.* 6 (2015).
9. Magesh V, Harikrishnan P, Kingsly Jeba Singh D. Finite element analysis of slot wall deformation on stainless steel and titanium orthodontic brackets during simulated palatal root torque, *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 153(4), 481-488 (2018).
10. Harikrishnan P, Magesh V, Ajayan AM, et al., Finite element analysis of torque induced orthodontic bracket slot deformation in various bracket-archwire contact assembly, *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 197, 105748 (2020).
11. Magesh V, Harikrishnan P, Kingsly Jeba Singh D. Experimental evaluation of orthodontic bracket slot deformation to simulated torque, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. H.* 235(8), 940-946 (2021).
12. Harikrishnan P, Magesh V. Finite element analysis of Tie wings rotation – A new phenomenon in orthodontic bracket-archwire contact assembly during simulated torque, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. H.* 236(11), 1626-1634 (2022).
13. Harikrishnan P, Magesh V. Comparative analysis of bracket deformation in tie wings and slot region during simulated torque by finite element analysis, *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 160(4), 588-593 (2021).
14. Harikrishnan P, Magesh V. Stress distribution and deformation in six tie wings Orthodontic bracket during simulated tipping – A finite element analysis, *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 200, 105835 (2021).
15. Elsaka SE, Hammad SM, Ibrahim NF. Evaluation of stresses developed in different bracket-cement-enamel systems using finite element analysis with in vitro bond strength tests, *Prog Orthod.* 15,1-8 (2014).
16. Major TW, Carey JP, Nobes DS et al., Deformation and warping of the bracket slot in select self-ligating orthodontic brackets due to an applied third order torque, *J Orthod.* 39: 25-33 (2012).